

Stakeholder Meeting Report 2025

Research Data Management Training for NFDI

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Background Information

On 29 November 2025, the first stakeholder meeting organised by the RDMTraining4NFDI team (ZB MED and TH Cologne) and its cooperating partners, took place virtually. Those invited to this meeting included interested individuals from all consortia of the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI), data competencies centres¹, state initiatives and other stakeholders who were interested in informing themselves and discussing with the Research Data Management (RDM) community the needs and requirements for a certification process on RDM competencies within the NFDI. The invitation was sent via the Section Training & Education (EduTrain), the DINI/nestor UAG network group and the EduTrain's Working Group 5 channel on Rocket Chat on 8 September 2025. While registration was preferred, it was not required in order to lower the barrier for participants to attend the meeting. A reminder was sent via the listed Rocket Chat channels on 25 November 2025. In total, 83 participants registered, and were contacted personally, including sending access details and a link to the 'work in progress' document regarding a credentialing framework to inform them in advance of certification options if they wished. A total of 67 participants from different NFDI consortia, data competence centers and state initiatives took part in the stakeholder meeting.

The stakeholder meeting was held via Zoom and lasted 2.5 hours, including a 15-minute break. The meeting began with a brief introduction to the RDMTraining4NFDI project, followed by a 5-minute presentation on the content blueprint² and certification³. After this, there was a 1:20-hour working session in breakout groups using Miro boards: Conceptual Open Educational Resources (OER), Technical OER, Certification (German), Certification (English). The meeting concluded with a plenary wrap-up of the breakout sessions.

Overall, the main goals of the stakeholder meeting were:

- Discussing the requirements needed to improve the alignment of RDM training materials with aspects of OER and the FAIR principles
- Discussing the requirements for implementing a learning path
- Taking a step towards a community-driven understanding of the criteria for standardisation within the NFDI
- Identifying expectations, needs and requirements for certification options within the NFDI

This report will summarise the findings of the stakeholder meeting.

Results

The findings of the stakeholder meeting will be clustered according to the four breakout groups by first sharing the raw data (Miro boards) and then the summary, which was

¹ Funding programme "Datenkompetenzen in der Wissenschaft" including the establishment of data competencies centres:

https://www.bmftr.bund.de/DE/Forschung/Wissenschaftssystem/Forschungsdaten/DatenkompetenzenInDerWissenschaft/datenkompetenzeninderwissenschaft_node.html

² Bock and Kneib, 2025a.

³ Bock *et al.*, 2025b.

presented in the plenary session. The Miro boards were closed for editing directly after the meeting and were not intended for reuse. The summaries represent the topics themselves, without any discussion or transfer, since this report aims to provide an overview of the meeting.

Conceptual OER

Fig. 1 Opportunities through standardisation

Fig. 2 Challenges of standardisation

Fig. 3 Needs from the community

Fig. 4 Key findings on Conceptual OER

The participants in the breakout out session “Conceptual OER”⁴ agreed that the community should distinguish clearly between mandatory and optional information for OER materials.

Possible information elements include:

- DOI
- scripts
- documentation
- authors
- date
- version
- target group
- keywords related to the topic

The group concluded that it might be useful to provide the DOI and licence on each page, while information such as date and version still needs to be discussed. The participants also realised that metadata should be categorised into two types: metadata that should be included in the material itself and metadata that can be provided on a linked page, as it is not

⁴ Miro board: Conceptual OER: https://miro.com/app/live-embed/uXjVJtSmfP4=?embedMode=view_only_without_ui&moveToViewport=480%2C-398%2C2575%2C1449&embedId=450563471282.

as immediately necessary. There were comments that the group should share more resources within their consortium and projects. The need for quality identifiers has also been brought up in the discussion.

Technical OER

Fig. 5 Opportunities on Technical OER

Fig. 6 Challenges to be solved on Technical OER

Fig. 7 Requirements to consider on Technical OER

Fig. 8 Key findings of the breakout session on Technical OER

The breakout session on Technical OER⁵ highlighted that many technical requirements for reusable and sustainable OER are well understood, while concrete solutions are often still lacking. Participants identified opportunities in standardised technical workflows, modular OER structures and the consistent use of open formats and licences to improve interoperability and reuse across institutions. Key challenges include the absence of shared technical standards, limited guidance on suitable platforms, and missing mechanisms for feedback, quality assurance and usage tracking. Difficulties were also noted with the reusability of certain formats, particularly video materials, as well as with the consistent documentation of technical dependencies, versioning and licences. The group emphasised that the goal was not to define ready solutions but to clearly identify gaps and areas requiring coordinated action. Providing guidance on technical best practices, open formats and documentation standards was seen as an important next step for improving Technical OER within the NFDI context.

⁵ Miro board: Technical OER: https://miro.com/app/live-embed/uXjVJpCSkdq=?embedMode=view_only_without_ui&moveToViewport=394%2C-2155%2C5336%2C3003&embedId=152654635505.

Certification (language German)

Fig. 9 Opportunities for RDMT's Credentialing Framework (in German)

Fig. 10 Challenges for RDMT's Credentialing Framework (in German)

Fig. 11 Communities' needs/requirements for RDMT's Credentialing Framework (in German)

Which findings does the group want to present to the plenary

Fig. 12 Key findings of the breakout session on RDMT's credentialing framework (in German)

One key conclusion from the German discussion round on RDMT's credentialing framework⁶ was that subject-specific content should be central to discussions on RDM certification and that the relevant stakeholders for subject-specific certification need to be identified and brought together. The group also raised the question of how Higher Education Institutes (HEI) and other stakeholders⁷ without a direct link to the NFDI can be meaningfully included as excluding them could potentially lead to a disconnect between target groups. At the same time, even HEI and stakeholders affiliated with the NFDI often have limited awareness of its activities and involvements, suggesting that the current bottom-up approach practiced within the NFDI might not function properly. As a result, there may be a need for more consistent guidelines across participating institutions. At the same time, to ensure the continued implementation of the NFDI's bottom up approach, it is essential that the diverse interests of the entire RDM community are adequately represented, that decisions are not driven by historically established networks, and that decision making processes remain transparent and open. Another important point highlighted was that institutional management levels need to recognise the importance of certification, actively promote and support its implementation.

⁶ Miro board: Certification [German]:

https://miro.com/app/live-embed/uXjVJpBy8gE=?embedMode=view_only_without_ui&moveToViewport=141%2C-1069%2C3300%2C1858&embedId=615822728378.

⁷ Such as data competence centres, industry and schools.

Finally, efforts should be made to build bridges between RDM in science and industry to create trusted standards and practices.

Certification (language English)

Fig. 13 Opportunities for RDMT's Credentialing Framework (in English)

Fig. 14 Challenges for RDMT's Credentiaing Framework (in English)

Fig. 15 Needs from the community to be considered by RDMTraining4NFDI (in English)

Fig. 16 Key findings of the breakout session on Certification (in English)

One of the most pressing questions in the breakout session on certification (in English)⁸ was what should be certified. People? Individual skill levels? Learning materials, programmes or trainers/institutions? There was agreement that certification would promote the professionalisation of people in RDM. An opportunity is to establish a common, reliable standard (“what does a person in this role / career stage need to be able to do”) that enables the comparability of qualifications and allows an official recognition of achievements (quality framework). At the same time, it was recognised that the development of quality criteria for certification should be a community-driven process or developed by an expert group. A ‘NFDI stamp’, a ‘quality stamp’ from the NFDI or a NFDI-‘badge’ to identify certifications was mentioned as an idea to highlight certificated entities. The participants agreed that it was important to discuss this together with the NFDI. They also agreed that the NFDI itself should exchange ideas and cooperate with other institutions. There are already certifying institutions that offer quality criteria and certification programmes. The

⁸ Miro board: Certification [English]: https://miro.com/app/live-embed/uXjVJpCK6n4=?embedMode=view_only_without_ui&moveToViewort=-2057%2C-644%2C3314%2C1865&embedId=626022043511.

RDM certification course⁹ was mentioned, as well as the TÜV¹⁰ as an established, trustworthy authority.

One challenge is determining what the certification process should look like and which step should come first. There was agreement that lessons should be learned from those who have already gone through this process (“Leverage on existing successful certifications”, “(...) There's no need to reinvent the wheel (...”). There was general consent that the process should be lightweight and that it needs to be clarified who will pay for the certification. Quality takes time and effort – the added value of certification must be clear. The RDMT team was advised to evaluate which certificates are reliable. Information on microcredentials¹¹ was shared.

Conclusion

Overall, stakeholder meetings have indicated a high level of interest within the RDM community in a more coordinated approach to cross-sectional, interdisciplinary RDM training. Key challenges include the absence of shared technical standards and guidance on suitable platforms, as well as missing mechanisms for feedback and quality assurance, particularly with regard to Technical OER, where concrete implementation strategies and shared workflows are still lacking.

The RDM community also expressed a high level of interest in a certification framework to recognise the competencies of RDM multipliers. A central question raised in the English breakout session was what should be certified: individuals, defined skill levels, learning materials, programmes or institutions. There was agreement that certification would promote the professionalisation of individuals working in RDM. However, the results also show that a lack of quality characteristics is one barrier to establishing a certification process within the NFDI. The development of quality criteria for certification should be a community-driven process or carried out by an expert group. Despite the identified challenges, the RDM community emphasised the importance of incremental steps towards a certification process to foster a more coordinated and standardised approach to RDM training within the NFDI.

Outlook

The results from the stakeholder meeting's breakout sessions will be included in the certification report¹². They will also be incorporated into the RDMTraining4NFDI integration proposal¹³.

The present document is primarily descriptive and observational in nature. It reports on the discussions and outcomes of the meeting without providing interpretation or

⁹ certificate course “Zertifikatskurs Forschungsdatenmanagement”:

https://www.th-koeln.de/weiterbildung/zertifikatskurs-forschungsdatenmanagement_82048.php

¹⁰ TÜV (Technischer Überwachungsverein) is a well established German inspection and certification body for products, processes and management systems.

¹¹ The following link was shared in the breakout session:

<https://www.hrk-modus.de/themen/microcredentials/>.

¹² Bock *et al.*, 2025b.

¹³ Wohltmann *et al.*, 2026.

recommendations. Future documents, including the certification report and subsequent project outputs, will build on these observations and additionally include analytical reflections, interpretations, and concrete suggestions for the further development of a certification process for RDM competencies.

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Author Contributions

Sina Bock, Mirjam Blümm and Marco Uebachs, provided the content for the meeting with support from Base4NFDI, Sina Bock and Mareike Wohltmann organized the meeting, Sina Bock created the miro-boards, Mareike Wohltmann, Sina Bock, Mirjam Blümm, Rabea Müller and Marco Uebachs wrote the report with support from Base4NFDI. All authors supported during the meeting and commented on the report.

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Miro board: Conceptual OER:

https://miro.com/app/live-embed/uXjvJtSmfP4=?embedMode=view_only_without_ui&moveToViewport=-497%2C-610%2C2683%2C1510&embedId=972895526182.

Miro board: Technical OER:

https://miro.com/app/live-embed/uXjVJpCSkdg=?embedMode=view_only_without_ui&moveToViewport=394%2C-2155%2C5336%2C3003&embedId=152654635505.

Miro board: Certification [German]:

https://miro.com/app/live-embed/uXjVJpBy8gE=?embedMode=view_only_without_ui&moveToViewport=141%2C-1069%2C3300%2C1858&embedId=615822728378.

Miro board: Certification [English]:

https://miro.com/app/live-embed/uXjVJpCK6n4=?embedMode=view_only_without_ui&moveToViewport=-2057%2C-644%2C3314%2C1865&embedId=626022043511.